

Deliverable 1.2.2 - Quality requirements and categories of Belgian entities

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¹ CRediT taxonomy <https://credit.niso.org/implementing-credit/>

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 Royal Museums
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ROYAL MUSEUMS OF ART AND HISTORY
KONINKLIJKE MUSEA VOOR KUNST EN GESCHIEDENIS
MUSÉES ROYAUX D'ART ET D'HISTOIRE

Executive Summary

Essentially we have to integrate the data of the partners, make it available under a persistent identifier according to the FAIR data principles and maintain the integration throughout the operation of the MetaBelgica platform. Early on we identified the risk of disagreement when trying to maintain detailed information about authority records in a collaborative fashion. Therefore we decided to include only a minimal number of data fields for authority records, basically enough to disambiguate records. Concretely the name and name spelling variants of a person, identifier of the MetaBelgica partner institution, other international identifiers, birth and death date as well as birth and death place. Due to their scientific value, nationality and gender information might be (internally) added in the future.

We analyzed more than **930,000** person authority records from The Royal Library of Belgium (KBR), more than **82,000** person authority records from The Royal Institute of Cultural Heritage (KIK-IRPA), more than **3,400** person authority records from the Royal Museums of Fine Arts of Belgium (KMSKB) and more than **7,400** person authority records from the Royal Museums of Art and History. Additionally we developed open source tools to standardize date values according to the Extended Date Time Format (EDTF) and place names with the help of Geonames.

More than 50% of KBR's person authorities contain an ISNI identifier which eases a future data integration. However, as the largest source of authority data, KBR also contains comparably low amounts of filled data fields compared to some of the other data sources. The smallest data source KMSKB has the best curated data in terms of percentages of filled data fields.

We have categorized the previously standardized authority data into nine data quality categories that will guide further data enrichment and integration. We plan to match as many records as possible based on rich metadata or ISNI identifiers with other trusted data sources. In addition, we will manually standardize values that could not be standardized automatically. Finally, many records do not provide any metadata other than the name; we will upload these records to the MetaBelgica Wikibase with an appropriate annotation that the records are of poor quality. Enriching and linking these records will become long-term goals that can be achieved with Wikibase, and we can focus on enriching and integrating data of the other quality categories.

We also defined Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) related to data quality. These KPIs will help us to continuously measure the added value of data enrichment in MetaBelgica.

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	4
Table of Contents	5
1. Introduction	6
2. Data sources	6
Royal Library of Belgium (KBR)	7
Royal Museums of Fine Arts of Belgium (KMSKB)	7
Royal Museums of Art and History (KMKG)	8
Royal Institute for Cultural Heritage (KIK-IRPA)	9
3. Data extraction	9
3.1 KBR data extraction	10
3.2 KIK-IRPA data extraction	12
3.3 KMSKB data extraction	14
3.4 KMKG data extraction	15
4. Datafields overview	18
5. Data cleaning	20
5.1 Uniformizing dates	21
5.2 Uniformizing place names	24
6. Initial statistics of cleaned data	26
6.1 Date statistics	26
6.2 Place statistics	34
6.3 Spatial temporal analysis	37
7. Quality categories and Key Performance Indicators	39
7.1 Quality categories	39
7.2 Key Performance Indicators	42
8. Conclusion	43
References	45
Appendix	45
A. Date parsing configuration	46

1. Introduction

The goal of MetaBelgica is to combine the efforts of initially four Belgian Federal Scientific Institutes in terms of data management for authority data. Each institution has their own focus and collections, but due to the nature of the data there is an overlap of authority records. Yet this overlap is not explicitly annotated and additionally each institution uses their own authority management tools, data models and data curation guidelines.

This deliverable introduces the different data sources and reports on our efforts to analyze, enrich and standardize the existing data. To reach our goal of shared entity management, we have to clean and uniformize the data. On the one hand to establish a common standard to ease inter institutional data analysis and on the other hand, to ease later data integration based on metadata. Software libraries developed at KBR or specifically for the MetaBelgica project are listed in the references in case they are mentioned in the text. The Jupyter notebook and other Python software components to analyze the data is available at <https://github.com/MetaBelgica/analysis> (DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.15120909](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15120909))

In section 2 we introduce the different data sources. In section 3 we describe how we extract data from the different data sources. In section 4 we list basic statistics about the number of person records, including the number of certain data fields that can be used to measure a potential overlap. In section 5 we describe how we cleaned and uniformized the data. In section 6 we provide initial statistics of the standardized data. In section 7 we define different quality categories that guide us in the enrichment and integration of the data and we define Key Performance Indicators to measure the quality improvement process. We discuss and conclude in section 8.

In the remainder of the report we either use the single official abbreviation of a partner institution or for simplicity the official Dutch abbreviation. Thus for the Royal Library, KBR, for the Royal Institute of Cultural Heritage KIK-IRPA, for the Royal Museums of Fine Arts of Belgium, KMSKB, and for the Royal Museums of Art and History, KMKMG.

2. Data sources

Each institution works in one or more systems that store the data in different formats. This section provides some basic information about the systems of each partner.

Royal Library of Belgium (KBR)

As the national scientific library of Belgium, KBR mainly receives publications via legal deposit. From its roughly 8 million physical documents, 3.5 million are catalogued and digital metadata is available. Next to those bibliographic data, KBR also holds several patrimonial collections such as Coins and Medals, Maps and Plans or Manuscripts and Rare books. Additionally, KBR continues to digitise collections that are made accessible via the platforms Belgica, BelgicaPress and BelgicaPeriodicals.

Since 2019, KBR uses the Software Syracuse from the French company Archimed. All metadata, including metadata of the patrimonial collections, is stored in MARC21 and can be exported in various formats such as MARCXML or CSV via the back office catalogue. Bibliographic and authority metadata can be accessed by the public via the Online Public Access Catalog (OPAC) at <https://opac.kbr.be>². For current internal use, the system also provides separate Search/Retrieval via URL (SRU) API endpoints (Z39.50) for bibliographic records and authority records and additionally OAI-PMH.

Royal Museums of Fine Arts of Belgium (KMSKB)

The management of KMSKB's collections is currently carried out through five databases divided into two categories: 1) the **art collection** (FABRITIUS and LOANA), and 2) the **documentary collections** (Library, ACAB, and ARMFAB). These systems are not connected to each other. As part of the Metabelgica project, the KMSKB are primarily focusing on the art collections, with plans to later integrate the documentary data.

Art collection

- For about twenty years, the works of art from the KMSKB have been registered in the **FABRITIUS** catalogue (Fine Arts Brussels Internet & Intranet Users), integrated into the VUBIS-Smart software of the company INFOR (now Axiell). The data structure follows the J. Paul Getty Trust's CDWA (Categories for the Description of Works of Art) standard, and is implemented in MARC. In 2021-2022, the FABRITIUS infrastructure was updated, now enabling data entry via a browser thanks to the V-smart Air web module. In 2022-2023, a new online catalogue (WebOpacAir) was developed and opened to the public. The data is encoded in Dutch, French, and partially in English. To date, more than 12,000 records are included in FABRITIUS. Data can be exported in XML format.

² The KBR OPAC page about the Belgian writer Stefan Hertmans:
<https://opac.kbr.be/LIBRARY/doc/AUTHORITY/14159426>

- The **LOANA** catalogue (Intranet Users and Loaned Artworks) is dedicated to works on long-term loan from the Museums. Although it uses the same structure as FABRITIUS, it is only searchable internally and is not actively used. The data is encoded in Dutch and French. To date, more than 220 records have been included in LOANA. Those data can be exported in XML format.

Documentary collections

- The **library catalog** runs on V-smart Air and can be accessed via an [Iguana-based website](#).
- The catalog of the **AMRBAB** (Archives of the Royal Museums of Fine Arts of Belgium) provides access to **institutional archives**. It can be accessed via a [web portal](#). AtOM (Access to Memory) is the [underlying system](#). It is an open source application for describing and accessing online archives that meets today's needs.
- The **ARCHIBALD** catalogue (ARCHives of Belgian Arts Letters and Documents) presents documents from the fonds and collections of **the Archives of Contemporary Art in Belgium (AACB)**. This is a VUBIS-Smart product that no longer meets the data management requirements for archives, it can be accessed via a [webopac](#). The AACB is currently preparing a data migration in order to store and share the AACB in an AtOM infrastructure similar to the Institutional archive system.

Royal Museums of Art and History (KMKG)

The Museum's collections span European and national archaeology, Medieval to 17th-century furniture, Art Nouveau, and world cultures from Asia, the Americas, and the Middle East. Since 2017, the museum has managed its digital collections through a web-based CMS, MuseumPlus RIA, developed by the Swiss company Zetcom Group. This system centrally documents 260,000 object records, covering around 40 collections.

The museum follows several standards, including Spectrum and CDWA, to catalog the collections and connect them with other systems. Object data can be exported in formats such as CSV and LIDO. The API provides full and secure access to the MuseumPlus data structure, supporting both data import and export.

MuseumPlus also includes a dedicated "Authors" module to manage creators (organizations or cultures) of objects, detailing their roles and functions. Currently, this module contains 11,000 authors, 1,000 cultures, and 300 organizations (including manufacturers, museum institutions, and abbeys).

Approximately one-third of the collections are available in the online catalog [Carmentis](#), where objects are described and linked with scientific, multilingual thesauri. The museum

also maintains various libraries and archives, with collections organized by museum department.

Books, monographs, catalogs, and other scientific documentation are managed in separate information systems, accessible online via [LIMO](#). The literature module within the CMS retrieves data from LIMO, allowing consultation of detailed descriptions of books and authors.

As part of the Metabelgica project, the KMKG currently prioritizes collections but plans to integrate documentary data from the library and archives in the future.

Royal Institute for Cultural Heritage (KIK-IRPA)

The Royal Institute for Cultural Heritage (KIK-IRPA) documentary collections (photographs, publications, scientific archives and online resources) span art preserved in Belgian public and private collections and monuments. This covers from architecture to Belgian and European painting, sculpture, decorative arts, prints and photographs (from Middle Age to 20th century), to Ancient Archeology artefacts, and artworks from Asia, the Americas, and the Middle East. All these documentary collections are largely accessible online through our platform [BALaT](#) (Belgian Art Links and Tools).

Books (monographs, catalogs...), journals and other scientific publications from the library are managed in the same information system, as well intervention files, all largely accessible online via [BALaT](#).

Since 1998, KIK-IRPA uses the Software Adlib from the Dutch company of the same name, and will migrate to Axiell in the next few years. Bibliographic and authority metadata can be accessed by the public via the Online Public Access Catalog (OPAC) at [BALaT](#)³.

3. Data extraction

This section elaborates on how we extracted data from the different data sources. We requested data from each partner in its native XML-based format to avoid data loss due to possible vendor-specific data transformation into more common table-based formats. For a uniform processing of the data, we use a generic script to extract data fields from data source-specific XML into a simple Comma Separated Values (CSV) format. During this

³ KIK-IRPA OPAC page about the painter Pieter Bruegel I: <https://balat.kikirpa.be/people.php?preref=68>

conversion with an open source script (*Lieber, 2025c*), we keep track of possible 1:n relationships and provide a transparent way of transforming the data.

By using the extraction script one gets a main CSV output file as well as one CSV file per extracted column. The main CSV output file contains one column for each extracted CSV field. Column values are Python lists since a field can occur more than once. Therefore the other files exist to resolve 1:n relationships. For example, for every alternate name one row is added to the `alternateName.csv` file.

If a column is marked with the `valueType "date"`, the column will not only be extracted, but also transformed based on the provided date configuration, see section 5.2 and listing A.1 in the appendix. In the following we briefly describe how we configured the generic script for the different data sources as well as other preparation steps we performed.

3.1 KBR data extraction

We obtained a MARCXML file of 717MB via the *Syracuse* back-office catalog of KBR and the search query shown in listing 3.1.1 that fetches authorities of type person (APEP) that are linked to at least one document (NBDL). As of end-January, KBR manages 944,514 person authorities from which 940,143 are linked to at least one document.

Listing 3.1.1: KBR back-office search query for person authorities that are linked to at least one document.

```
TYPN="APEP" AND NBDL>"0"
```

Standardized values for birth date and death date are encoded in MARC field 043\$f, respectively 043\$g. However, the MARC field 100\$d also contains date information that either was not yet added to MARC field 043 or was not supposed to be added there. The latter case refers to a flourish date that only gives an approximation to the lifetime of the person: a date indicating that the person certainly published something in that year, meaning the person was alive during or before that year. Dates in 100\$d follow the format "birthyear-deathyear", respectively for flourish dates "first known publication year - last known publication year".

After downloading the MARCXML data, we extracted CSV files with the mentioned open source script and the configuration shown in listing 3.1.2. Afterwards we split dates of the field 100\$d into separate columns for birth year and death year, respectively first known publication year and last known publication year. By joining the CSV file with the 100\$d date

information and the CSV with 046 date information, we can filter authorities that do not yet have a 046 date, but that do have a 100\$d date (certain date or uncertain flourish date).

Listing 3.1.2: The CSV from XML extraction configuration for KBR data

```
{
  "recordTagString": "record",
  "recordTag": "marc:record",
  "recordIDExpression": "./marc:controlfield[@tag=\"001\"]",
  "recordIDPrefix": "kbr|",
  "recordIDColumnName": "autID",
  "dataDelimiter": ";",
  "dataFields": [
    {
      "columnName": "name",
      "expression": "./marc:datafield[@tag=\"100\"]/marc:subfield[@code=\"a\"]",
      "valueType": "text"
    },
    {
      "columnName": "alternateNames",
      "expression": "./marc:datafield[@tag=\"400\"]/marc:subfield[@code=\"a\"]",
      "valueType": "text"
    },
    {
      "columnName": "pseudonyms",
      "expression": "./marc:datafield[@tag=\"500\"]/marc:subfield[@code=\"a\"]",
      "valueType": "text"
    },
    {
      "columnName": "dates100d",
      "expression": "./marc:datafield[@tag=\"100\"]/marc:subfield[@code=\"d\"]",
      "valueType": "text"
    },
    {
      "columnName": "birthDate",
      "expression": "./marc:datafield[@tag=\"046\"]/marc:subfield[@code=\"f\"]",
      "valueType": "date",
      "keepOriginal": "true"
    },
    {
      "columnName": "deathDate",
      "expression": "./marc:datafield[@tag=\"046\"]/marc:subfield[@code=\"g\"]",
      "valueType": "date",
      "keepOriginal": "true"
    },
    {
      "columnName": "birthPlace",
      "expression": "./marc:datafield[@tag=\"370\"]/marc:subfield[@code=\"a\"]",

```

```

"valueType": "text",
"keepOriginal": "true"
},
{
"columnName": "deathPlace",
"expression": "./marc:datafield[@tag=\"370\"]/marc:subfield[@code=\"b\"]",
"valueType": "text",
"keepOriginal": "true"
},
{
"columnName": "isni",
"expression": "./marc:datafield[@tag=\"024\"]/marc:subfield[@code=\"2\" and (text()=\"isni\"
or text()=\"ISNI\")]/../marc:subfield[@code=\"a\"]",
"valueType": "text"
},
{
"columnName": "viaf",
"expression": "./marc:datafield[@tag=\"024\"]/marc:subfield[@code=\"2\" and (text()=\"viaf\"
or text()=\"VIAF\")]/../marc:subfield[@code=\"a\"]",
"valueType": "text"
}
]
}

```

3.2 KIK-IRPA data extraction

We received two XML files from KIK-IRPA that were exported from their Adlib XPlus system, one file of 483.5MB about persons authorities and one file of 54.3MB containing a taxonomy of geo entities. The former contains place names as text and optionally a link to a geo identifier of the other file.

We extracted data solely from the person authority file with the configuration shown in listing 3.2.1. Besides links to hierarchically higher geo entities, the second file does not provide a specific added value for our tasks at hand. We standardize place names with the help of geonames anyway, therefore we can also use the place name indicated as text in the person authority file.

In contrast to KBR data where we did not have to filter for person records as we already indicated the type of authority at the stage of exporting, we have to filter the KIK-IRPA data. This is because in the KIK-IRPA data every alternate spelling of a person is recorded as a

separate XML record. Hence we filter records that represent the *approved preferred term* record with the configuration entry “recordFilter”. Please note that we still have access to alternate spellings of an authority record as those are also added as string values in the preferred term record.

Listing 3.2.1: The CSV from XML extraction configuration for KIK-IRPA data.

```
{
  "recordTag": "record",
  "recordIDExpression": "./priref[@tag=\"%0\"]",
  "recordIDPrefix": "kik-irpa|",
  "recordIDColumnName": "autID",
  "recordFilter": {
    "expression": "./name.status/value[@lang=\"neutral\"]",
    "condition": "equals",
    "value": "1"
  },
  "dataFields": [
    {
      "columnName": "isni",
      "expression": "./PIDother/PID_other.source/value[text()=\"ISNI\"]/../../PID_other.non-URI_ID",
      "valueType": "text"
    },
    {
      "columnName": "name",
      "expression": "./name/value[@lang=\"en-GB\"]",
      "valueType": "text"
    },
    {
      "columnName": "alternateName",
      "expression": "./used_for/value[@lang=\"en-GB\"]",
      "valueType": "text"
    },
    {
      "columnName": "birthDate",
      "expression": "./birth.date.start",
      "valueType": "text"
    },
    {
      "columnName": "deathDate",
      "expression": "./death.date.start",
      "valueType": "text"
    },
    {
      "columnName": "birthPlace",
      "expression": "./birth.place/value[@lang=\"en-GB\"]",
      "valueType": "text",
      "keepOriginal": "true"
    }
  ]
}
```

```

{
  "columnName": "deathPlace",
  "expression": "./death.place/value[@lang=\"en-GB\"]",
  "valueType": "text",
  "keepOriginal": "true"
}
]
}
    
```

3.3 KMSKB data extraction

We received an export of the FABRITIUS database in MARCXML of 4.4MB. The full name of a person is usually stored in MARC field 100\$0 and the components of the name in separate fields in MARC field 110. However, we have noticed that a few authorities do only have the more specific name components in MARC field 110: first name in 110\$02 and last name in 110\$01. For cases where only more specific name components exist, we added the full name following the pattern “lastname, firstname” to the CSV after extraction. The configuration from listing 3.3.1 was used to extract the data from KMSKB.

There are many “anonymous” records for which only minimal data is provided that is not sufficient for identification. For example, many records have the name “Zuid-Nederlandse school”, indicating that this is an artist following that school, but it is not known who specifically. For now these records are not filtered out.

Listing 3.3.1: The CSV from XML extraction configuration for KMSKB data.

```

{
  "recordTag": "record",
  "recordIDExpression": "./controlfield[@tag=\"001\"]",
  "recordIDPrefix": "kmskb|",
  "recordIDColumnName": "autID",
  "dataFields": [
    {
      "columnName": "name",
      "expression": "./datafield[@tag=\"100\"]/subfield[@code=\"01\"]",
      "valueType": "text"
    },
    {
      "columnName": "nameComponents",
      "expression": "./datafield[@tag=\"110\"]",
      "valueType": "json",
    }
  ]
}
    
```

```
"subfields": [  
  {  
    "columnName": "lastName",  
    "expression": "./subfield[@code=\"01\"]",  
    "valueType": "text"  
  },  
  {  
    "columnName": "firstName",  
    "expression": "./subfield[@code=\"02\"]",  
    "valueType": "text"  
  }  
],  
{  
  "columnName": "birthDate",  
  "expression": "./datafield[@tag=\"200\"]/subfield[@code=\"01\"]",  
  "valueType": "date",  
  "keepOriginal": "true"  
},  
{  
  "columnName": "deathDate",  
  "expression": "./datafield[@tag=\"200\"]/subfield[@code=\"02\"]",  
  "valueType": "date",  
  "keepOriginal": "true"  
},  
{  
  "columnName": "birthPlace",  
  "expression": "./datafield[@tag=\"300\"]/subfield[@code=\"01\"]",  
  "valueType": "text"  
},  
{  
  "columnName": "deathPlace",  
  "expression": "./datafield[@tag=\"400\"]/subfield[@code=\"01\"]",  
  "valueType": "text"  
}  
]
```

3.4 KMKG data extraction

We received an XML export of 8,7MB. This export contains a single XML root element PersonList containing person records. The configuration from listing 3.4.1 was used to extract the data from KMKG.

Usually a record has at least one name of type “Nom original”, and optionally additional multilingual name spellings of types:

- “Terme FR/Term FR Nom”
- “Terme NL/Term NL Naam”
- “Terme EN/Term EN Name”

We use the “Nom original” field as name and the above listed term types as alternate spellings.

Listing 3.4.1: The CSV from XML extraction configuration for KMKG data.

```
{
  "recordTag": "Person",
  "recordIDExpression": "./ID",
  "recordIDColumnName": "autID",
  "recordIDPrefix": "kmg|",
  "dataFields": [
    {
      "columnName": "isni",
      "expression": "./URLList/URL/TypeURL[text()=\"ISNI\"]/../URL",
      "valueType": "isniURL"
    },
    {
      "columnName": "bnf",
      "expression": "./URLList/URL/TypeURL[text()=\"BNF\"]/../URL",
      "valueType": "bnfURL"
    },
    {
      "columnName": "name",
      "expression": "./NomsList/Noms/Typenom[text()=\"Nom original\"]/../Nom",
      "valueType": "text"
    },
    {
      "columnName": "alternateNames",
      "expression": "./NomsList/Noms/Typenom[starts-with(text(),\"Terme\"]/../Nom",
      "valueType": "text"
    },
    {
      "columnName": "gender",
      "expression": "./Sexe",
      "valueType": "text"
    },
    {
      "columnName": "nationality",
      "expression": "./Pays",

```

```

"valueType": "text"
},
{
  "columnName": "birthDate",
  "expression": "./DatesList/Dates/Typedate[text()='Date de naissance\']/../Datation",
  "keepOriginal": "true",
  "valueType": "date"
},
{
  "columnName": "deathDate",
  "expression": "./DatesList/Dates/Typedate[text()='Date de mort\']/../Datation",
  "keepOriginal": "true",
  "valueType": "date"
},
{
  "columnName": "birthPlace",
  "expression": "./DatesList/Dates/Typedate[text()='Date de naissance\']/..",
  "valueType": "json",
  "subfields": [
    {
      "columnName": "birthTown",
      "expression": "./Lieu",
      "valueType": "text"
    },
    {
      "columnName": "birthCountry",
      "expression": "./Pays",
      "valueType": "text"
    }
  ]
},
{
  "columnName": "deathPlace",
  "expression": "./DatesList/Dates/Typedate[text()='Date de mort\']/..",
  "valueType": "json",
  "subfields": [
    {
      "columnName": "deathTown",
      "expression": "./Lieu",
      "valueType": "text"
    },
    {
      "columnName": "deathCountry",
      "expression": "./Pays",
      "valueType": "text"
    }
  ]
}
]

```

}

4. Datafields overview

The integration of the data depends on the data fields that are in common. On the one hand we have data fields with international identifiers that could lead to a match, and on the other hand a combination of other fields. Please note that a match simply on a name does not suffice due to name ambiguity. A match by a combination of name and birth year for instance would be more reliable. A manual check afterwards remains necessary. Table 2 lists the number of person records per data source and how often certain data fields are filled in.

Table 2: Distribution of filled data fields per data source. The 17% respectively 11% increase of KBR date values are due to additionally cleaning and processing of a separate date field (see section 5.1 for more details)

Feature	KBR	KIK-IRPA	KMSKB	KMKG
Number of person records	939,958	82,059	3,471	7,483
with ISNI	513,825 (55%)	868 (1%)	0 (0%)	1,162 (16%)
with VIAF	8,822 (1%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
with birth date value	182,810 (19% +17%)	16,595 (20%)	2,858 (82%)	1,056 (14%)
with death date value	119,302 (13% +11%)	13,949 (17%)	2,511 (72%)	850 (11%)
with birth place value	21,148 (2%)	3,100 (4%)	2,694 (78%)	1,886 (25%)
with death place value	12,279 (1%)	2,705 (3%)	2,306 (66%)	1,447 (19%)

As we can see in figure 4.1, KBR has the most filled data fields in total numbers, It also has by far the most ISNI identifiers. This is, because compared to other data sources, KBR has by far

the largest number of person authorities. However, when comparing percentages, we noticed that KMSKB has the best curated data for anything but standard identifiers.

Interestingly, the number of filled birth dates and death dates for KMSKB is comparable and rather high, thus most person authority records from KMSKB are of already deceased people.

Figure 4.1: A radar chart in logarithmic scale showing the total number of filled data fields per data source. KBR as the largest source also has the highest total for every datafield, especially for ISNI identifiers. Please see figure 2 for percentages.

Figure 4.2: A radar chart showing the percentage of how often a certain datafield is filled per data source. KMSKB clearly has the most curated birth and death metadata, however, no ISNI or VIAF standard identifiers. KIK-IRPA provides some date information, but is less rich in place information. KBR scores well on ISNI identifiers and its percentage of date information is comparable to KIK-IRPA and KMKG. The latter provides more place information and has some ISNI identifiers.

5. Data cleaning

For a comparative data analysis as well as for a later data integration, the metadata fields should follow the same syntax. However, the data is multilingual and often follows internal standards. For example, the dates “January 1795”, “Janvier 1795” and “1795-01” describe the same date, but syntactically are different. In this section we describe how we

uniformized the data and provide initial statistics. In section 5.1 we elaborate on uniformizing dates and in section 5.2 on uniformizing place names.

5.1 Uniformizing dates

Authority data about persons contain the date of birth and in case the person already died, should contain the date of death. We try to parse existing dates and where possible transform dates with different precision to follow the Extended Date Time Format (EDTF). This date parsing is executed as part of the CSV extraction script when “date” is indicated as valueType of a column⁴.

Concretely we try to parse a date value based on different patterns. Either a “simple” pattern such as YYYY-MM-DD or DD/MM/YYYY, or a more complex pattern such as “November 1980”, “between 1976 and 1979”, or “ca. 1980”. If configured with the flag keepOriginal, the resulting 1:n CSV files keep the column of the originally found date next to the parsed data, additionally the rule used to parse the data is indicated as well. This helps in manually checking if everything was parsed correctly and gives insights into the used patterns.

Figure 5.1.1 shows the statistics about how often a certain date pattern was found for birth dates in each data source. Figure 5.1.2 shows the same for death dates accordingly. The scale is logarithmic as otherwise the type simplePattern, with its absolute high number, overshadows the occurrences of other patterns. We iteratively parsed the input data and adapted the patterns to identify more patterns. The pattern *year_and_text* is rather generic and often captures complete dates for which no more-specific pattern matches. Thus, examining the results from the *year_and_text* pattern often helped us to devise more specific patterns.

From figure 5.1.1 it is visible that many dates have full precision and already follow a standard notation: the pattern *simplePattern* is by far the most often matched pattern. In cases where a placeholder value such as “----” is used, we indicate this in the separate logfile of the parsing script. Most variety in date patterns is found for KBR, this is due to the parsing of an additional and less standardized datafield that among others contains approximate dates based on when a person was active (see description in section 3.1).

Table 5.1.1 lists the EDTF notations that we applied as well as examples of the previously non-standardized date values accordingly.

⁴ It is still unclear how to correctly represent BC dates <https://github.com/kbrbe/xml-to-csv/issues/17>

Figure 5.1.1: Statistics of date parsing for birth dates per data source, bar height in logarithmic scale.

Figure 5.1.2: Statistics of date parsing for birth dates per data source, percentages in logarithmic scale.

Table 5.1.1: Applied EDTF notations and a comma-separated list of examples for the pattern found in the data. Square brackets indicate a set from which one value applies.

EDTF example	Description	Examples found in the data
[..1770]	Before or in that year	Avant 1770, Flor. ca. 1770
[1970..]	That year or later	1970
[1970-04..]	That year and month or later (similarly the dots before the date to indicate that year and month or earlier)	1970-04
[1720..1740]	Between or in one of those years	Entre 1720 et 1740
[1970,1971]	One of the years	1970 ou 1971, 1605/06
1970~	Approximate year	c. 1625, ca. 1772, Vers 1970
1970?	Uncertain year	1970 ?
19XX	Date with century precision	19--, 19.----
1990	Date with year precision	1990
1990-04	Date with month precision	Décembre 1655, 1889-05---
1990-04-25	Date with day precision	25/04/1990

5.2 Uniformizing place names

Authority data about persons contain the birth place and in case the person already died, should contain the place of death. Usually this value is the name of a city written in a certain language, for example either “Anvers”, or “Antwerpen”. In this case Anvers is the French spelling of the city of Antwerp and Antwerpen the Dutch spelling. To normalize the place names we use the identifier and main spelling of the place according to the online database geonames.

The parsing of place names is done with an additional Python script (*Lieber, 2025a*) that sends the found spelling of a place to an internal API (*Lieber, 2025b*) that looks up the geoname identifier and main spelling of a place name variant in a local copy of the

geonames database (Alejandro Cornejo, 2025). Certain place names may exist in several countries, hence we added the possibility to additionally provide the name of the country in the API request to further filter possible results, see listing 5.2.1. This code listing shows API calls for the city of Bruges, the first call creates two results, Bruges in France and Bruges in Belgium. The other three calls illustrate how an additional country filter can be applied, i.e. by specifying a countryCode or a country name in any language known by Geonames.

Figure 5.2.1 shows statistics about API requests for places of birth and death. Either the API returns no search results, exactly one result or multiple results. Eventually, the API searches in all geoname places starting with the hierarchy level PPL, thus PPLC and others⁵. Hence certain places like London result in several search results, such as the city of London or Greater London. For such cases, the script can be configured to always choose one of the search results. However, there are also cases where it is less obvious, such as the Belgian place name Aalst: three places with the name Aalst exist in Belgium and hence we cannot make an automatic choice which Aalst should be taken as it depends on the case. We also encountered invalid values that usually are placeholder values such as “---”.

Listing 5.2.1: Various examples of calling the geoname-lookup API developed in the project (Lieber, 2025a).

<https://example.org/api/places?name=Bruges>

<https://example.org/api/places?name=Bruges&countryCode=BE>

<https://example.org/api/places?name=Bruges&countryName=Belgium>

<https://example.org/api/places?name=Bruges&countryName=Belgique>

⁵ GitHub repository for geoname lookup API (Lieber, 2025a): <https://github.com/kbrbe/geonames-lookup>

Figure 5.2.1: The types of API errors encountered when trying to standardize birth and death locations.

6. Initial statistics of cleaned data

In this section we provide insights into the data based on date and place information that would not have been possible without standardization, or at least not with a considerable effort. In section 6.1 we elaborate on dates, in section 6.2 on places and in section 6.3 we combine both in a spatial temporal analysis to highlight the historical aspect of the location data. Please note that the presented data is not representative for a data source as only a fraction of all data has metadata about dates or places and from that fraction only a subset could be standardized.

6.1 Date statistics

This section shows statistics about the precision of available birth and death dates as well as the spreading of birth and death dates over the decades per data source.

Date precision. After applying date transformations we obtained 203,319 standardized birth dates and 136,611 standardized death dates. Figure 6.1.1 and 6.1.2 show the precision of identified and standardized dates across data sources. Figure 6.1.3 and 6.1.4 show the same precision values but per data source. Even though a large part of the records does not have a date, there is at least the year precision if there is a date. Uncertain dates are only a smaller subset. There are more dates with day precision than uncertain dates for death dates

compared to birth dates. This likely comes from the fact that for KBR data we often only had flourish dates, thus a start and optional end year in which a person was active. From that information we could only infer that the person must have been born before the earliest mentioned year, no uncertain death year could be inferred. For example, a flourish date of “flor. 1830 - 1841” indicates that we know that the person published something in 1830 and in 1841, thus the person must have been born before 1830 which we express using EDTF as “[..1830]”.

Figure 6.1.1: The date precision of standardized EDTF birth dates.

Figure 6.1.2: The date precision of standardized EDTF death dates.

Figure 6.1.3: The date precision of standardized EDTF birth dates per data source.

Figure 6.1.4: The date precision of standardized EDTF death dates per data source.

Dates across decades. Figure 6.1.5 shows the distribution of birth dates per decade from the 15th century onwards. Figure 6.1.6 shows the same birth years per decade, but zooms in into the data from the 18th century onwards. Similarly figures 6.1.7 and 6.1.8 show the same decades for death dates. As described earlier, in total numbers KBR provides the most birth and death dates. We can also see that KBR maintains many contemporary person records, probably due to legal deposit, whereas the other data sources focus more on earlier time periods.

Figure 6.1.5: The number of known birth dates across all data sources per decade since the 16th century.

Figure 6.1.6: The number of known birth dates across all data sources per decade since the 19th century.

Figure 6.1.7: The number of known death dates across all data sources per decade since the 16th century.

Figure 6.1.8: The number of known death dates across all data sources per decade since the 19th century.

6.2 Place statistics

In this section we provide insights into standardized place names by showing the distribution of countries with respect to birth and death places as well as the top 10 birth and death places in the data.

Figure 6.2.1 shows the distribution of combined birth and death places per country. Besides Belgium, people in the dataset were born or did die in neighboring countries or at least in other European countries. Almost half of the people (from which we know and from which we could standardize related place information) were born and/or died in what nowadays is Belgium. Instead of coming from villages across the country, the comparison between the left and the right circle illustrate that those people were born or died in a few more famous places such as Brussels, Ghent or Liège (see also figure 6.2.2). Whereas this could hint that those places might have been some cultural hubs attracting authors or artists, it is also likely that there is a bias: our analysis is based on a subset of the data and that subset could simply contain more commonly known artists from those places. Figure 6.2.2 shows the proportions of birth and death place by country per country. So basically a breakdown of the left circle of figure 6.2.1.

Figure 6.2.3 zooms into the actual place names of the countries. Comparing the previously mentioned figures with figure 6.2.3, we can see that the different data sources have a similar focus in terms of where persons were born. Even though there is some variety in places of birth, the same major cities reappear in all data sources. This is similar to figure 6.2.4 which shows the top 10 of death places. What pops out is that certain Dutch placenames occur often in KMSKB's data, showing a focus on the Netherlands.

Country of peoples' birth and death places

Country of unique birth and death places

Figure 6.2.1: The distribution of birth and death places per country (left) and the distribution of unique birth and death places per country (right). For example, if people were born or did die in many places of a country, the countries' proportion will be bigger in the right circle compared to if they were born or did die in only a few famous places of the country.

Comparison of Birth and Death Places (Top 10 Countries)

Figure 6.2.2: The number of times a person was born or did die in a country per country.

Top 10 Placenames for Birthplaces Per DataSource

Figure 6.2.3: The top 10 of birth places per data source.

Figure 6.2.4: The top 10 of death places per data source

6.3 Spatial temporal analysis

In this section we briefly highlight the spatial temporal potential of the data. Place names are standardized with geonames which also provides information about the country. However, Belgium has only existed since 1830 and based on the standardized birth and death dates we can also identify persons that were born or did die in places that now are in Belgium, but which might have been in different countries before.

To this end we have identified 1,984 persons in our data that were born in nowadays Belgium, but before 1830. Figure 6.3.1 shows the top 20 nowadays Belgian place names per decade. A common place of birth is the city of Antwerp which was part of several kingdoms and countries over time. Together with spatial temporal reference lists, our spatial temporal data could be analyzed further which adds a new layer of information to the data and allows the users of the data to answer more research questions.

Birthplaces per Decade (Before 1830) - Top 20 Places

Figure 6.3.1: The top 20 places of birth in nowadays Belgium before 1830

7. Quality categories and Key Performance Indicators

The previous sections described how we could enrich and standardize the data and have provided examples about what kind of analysis are possible after data standardization. The data integration planned for a future deliverable depends on as much standardized metadata as possible to identify the overlap of persons. Additionally, any added or standardized data is an added value for the different MetaBelgica partner institutions and their respective catalogs. In section 7.1 we discuss different data quality categories to guide further data enrichment and data integration. In section 7.2 we define several Key Performance Indicators to initially measure the data quality of each data source individually and be able to later measure the evolution and added value of MetaBelgica.

7.1 Quality categories

The data integration strategy depends on the richness of the data, which varies as seen in the previous sections. In this section we define nine data quality categories and divide the analyzed data into the different categories for further data enrichment and integration.

Table 7.1.1 lists nine data quality categories and provides a data integration strategy per category. Each category requires a different approach to improve the data quality such as different tools and skills. Additionally not each data quality issue is equally urgent to be fixed, illustrated by the following two examples.

Example 1: A person's record already contains a place of birth, but this place could not automatically be enriched with a geonames identifier. We need to standardize the data and add a geonames identifier to ease matching with other records. Someone has to manually add the correct geonames identifier. This may require tools such as OpenRefine, Wikidata or other trusted data sources or some knowledge about the domain such as knowledge about the person or knowing the different language spellings of the place. This kind of enrichment is a “low hanging fruit”, it increases the quality of the data and likely is not too time consuming per record.

Example 2: A person's record already contains a date of birth, but this date is uncertain. Improving the precision of the date makes the record more complete and eases matching with other records. Someone has to manually research the correct date of birth. However, even with access to other trustworthy data sources, this information might not be available or would require time consuming research. This kind of enrichment is not urgent, having at least some standardized EDTF date is sufficient for matching.

Table 7.1.1: Data quality categories into which we can categorize our data with the goal to choose appropriate data integration strategy.

ID	Name	Integration strategy
MBQ1	External identifier and complete standardized metadata	Date integration via clustering together with data from category MBQ3. Analyze the clusters for duplicates within a data source and afterwards load clusters to Wikibase. Also clusters with one element are fine, rich data is available and the data makes a good target for later reconciliation of lower quality data.
MBQ2	External identifier but incomplete metadata	Enrich metadata via external identifier and databases such as Wikidata. Afterwards either include in clustering with data from MBQ1 and MBQ3 or reconcile with that data in the MetaBelgica Wikibase.
MBQ3	Complete standardized metadata but missing external identifier	Data integration via clustering together with data from category MBQ1 and uploading to Wikibase together with data of category MBQ1.
MBQ4	Unstandardized place	Analyze the geonames enrichment log and create assignment rules for ambiguous placenames about the same geonames entity. In case no automatic enrichment is possible, enrich the geonames identifiers manually. After enrichment records will be part of other quality categories depending on other metadata fields.
MBQ5	Date but not place and no external identifier	Identify missing place names based on name in relevant data sources (relevant data sources might be identified based on known date)
MBQ6	Place but no date and no external identifier	Identify missing dates based on name in relevant data sources (relevant data sources might be identified based on known place)
MBQ7	Missing metadata and no external identifier	Manually validate that the authority represents an entity and load it into the Wikibase with the additional annotation that the record needs manual curation and/or is a possible duplicate
MBQ8	Only a name, no metadata and no external identifier	Upload to MetaBelgica Wikibase with specific annotation that this is a work-in-progress record that needs enrichment and that it might be a possible duplicate
MBQ9	Not even a name	Discuss with colleagues from the partner institutions to fix the records in the data source or exclude from MetaBelgica integration

Figure 7.1.1 shows the distribution of data quality categories per data source. Only a tiny fraction of all data sources contains complete records with external standard identifiers and complete metadata (including death date and place). Most data sources have many records that fall into category MBQ8 which means only a name is available. Besides MBQ8, the different data sources show some distinctive patterns:

- **KBR's** data mainly falls into categories MBQ2 (47%) and MBQ5 (14%). Hence almost half of the authorities provide an external identifier which we can use to enrich other metadata fields (MBQ2). Sometimes there is a name and a date which we can use to research the missing place (MBQ5).
- Almost 80% of **KIK-IRPA's** data falls into category MBQ8. A similar amount of records as for KBR falls into category MBQ5 (17%) where dates are available, but no places.
- Half of **KMSKB's** data falls into category MBQ3, thus is already completely standardized and only misses standard identifiers. After missing place name standardization of category MBQ4 (17%) are fixed, likely more data will be category MBQ3.
- More than 60% of **KMKG's** data is in category MBQ8. Besides that, around 12% fall into category MBQ6, thus there is a standardized place, but no date information.

Concrete next steps, also outlined in table 7.1.1, should be to handle the category MBQ4 in parallel to semi-automatic enrichments of MBQ2. Afterwards the data can be re-classified and the categories MBQ1, MBQ2 and MBQ3 can be integrated, for example by using the Work-Set clustering algorithm's Python implementation (*Lieber, 2024*). Handling data quality categories MBQ5 and MBQ6 can also happen in parallel before data integration, alternatively, those data can be reconciled with OpenRefine against the combined data of MBQ1, MBQ2 and MBQ3 after uploading it to the MetaBelgica Wikibase.

Figure 7.1.1: The distribution of records' data quality categories from different data sources.

7.2 Key Performance Indicators

The aim of the MetaBelgica project is to set up a single authority database with high quality data of the four participating institutions. However, also the catalogs of the participating partners can profit from the data analysis and enrichment performed for MetaBelgica onboarding. This section lists several goals regarding increasing the data quality as well as Key Performance Indicators to continuously measure the improvement throughout the project. Please note that these KPIs concern the individual data sources, overall KPIs for MetaBelgica will be defined in a future deliverable focusing on the data integration. More information about what KPIs are can be found in related ISO documentation (*ISO Central Secretariat. 2015*)

Table 7.2.1 lists goals, KPIs and the initially calculated values of the KPIs. We are focusing on the identified metadata fields ISNI identifier, birth date and birth place. Information about death date or death place is deliberately not included as there is no gold standard for comparison and to measure completeness, i.e. if a person record exists, we know that there

is a birth date and birth place, however, a person might be still alive, resulting in empty information about death date and death place. Ideally we increase the number of ISNI identifiers at a data source if we find a link to a related KBR authority. Please note that for ISNI assignments of authorities that solely exist at partner institutions, KBR would require to provide a linked work which falls out of the scope of MetaBelgica. We also deal with historical authorities for which birth date or birth place information might be missing or are uncertain. Therefore we have KPIs related to the standardization of uncertain values. Identifying completely missing information may require lots of research beyond the scope of the MetaBelgica data integration. Nevertheless, we also include KPIs related to the existence of birth date and birth place information as some unknowns might be resolved via the data integration and identified matches with data from other MetaBelgica partners.

Table 7.2.1: Initially measured KPIs for the individual data sources

Goal	KPI	KBR	KIK-IRPA	KMSKB	KMKG
Increase the number of person authorities with ISNI identifier	Percentage of person authorities with ISNI	55%	1%	0%	16%
Increase the number of person authorities with birth date	Percentage of person authorities with birth date	19%	20%	82%	14%
	From which certain birth date	16%	100%	74%	12%
	From which uncertain birth date	4%	0%	8%	2%
Increase the number of person authorities with standardized birth place	Percentage of person authorities with textual birth place	2%	4%	78%	25%
	- from which standardized	59%	85%	84%	72%

8. Conclusion

This deliverable provided an overview of person authority data available at the initially four MetaBelgica partner institutions and reported on first standardization efforts as well as initial statistics.

Whereas person authority data from The Royal Library of Belgium (KBR) is the by far biggest data source, we found that in terms of percentages the least data fields are filled in compared to the other data sources. Yet, KBR as an ISNI registration agency has the most international identifiers which will ease further data integration. Data from the Royal Museums of Fine Arts of Belgium (KMSKB) is the best curated person authority data as

across the different data fields, more than 80% is filled in. The presented data standardization techniques for dates and placenames, namely the Extended Date Time Format (EDTF) for dates and geonames identifiers for placenames, enabled us to perform analyses across the data sources. Due to the heterogeneity of how data is filled in, often as free text, not all data could be standardized. However, with the help of semi-automatic means or old-fashioned manual curation we are able to further refine the standardization.

To this end, the presented categorization into nine different data quality categories will inform further data standardization, enrichment and eventually the data integration. Almost half of the KBR person authorities that miss metadata at least have an ISNI identifier and hence can be further enriched by semi-automatic reconciliation with other trusted data sources. Similarly half of the KMSKB person authorities that provide good quality metadata but miss a standard identifier, can be reconciled with other trusted data sources in order to obtain standard identifiers. As important is the knowledge that large parts of most data sources fall into a data quality category of low quality data: only a name is known, no other metadata or external identifiers. This is important to know as we do not have to focus on making this data perfect, but rather we can focus on improving data of other quality categories first. The low-quality data can be uploaded to the MetaBelgica Wikibase with appropriate annotations to indicate the quality category. The enrichment of that data can be tackled in the long-term by experienced catalogers and curators that can make use of sophisticated data management offered by the Wikibase-based MetaBelgica platform.

Future work will be applying identified data enrichment and data integration techniques to the different data quality categories. This will enable us to create an initial consolidated MetaBelgica dataset of person authorities that we can maintain in a Wikibase. Specific KPIs for the consolidated dataset will be defined and measured. Together with future measurements of data source-specific KPIs we are able to demonstrate the added value of the MetaBelgica project. In case the data sources provide the information, we also plan to add the columns nationality and gender which provide an added value for scientific research, that is part of the legal mission of all current MetaBelgica partners. Please note that not all of these data will be publicly available.

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Appendix

A. Date parsing configuration

The following configuration was used to parse date values during the data extraction phase.

The live version is available at

<https://github.com/kbrbe/xml-to-csv/blob/main/date-mapping.json>

Listing A1: The file date-mapping.json that was used as configuration to extract and transform dates from the partner data.

```
{
  "datePatterns": ["%Y", "(%Y)", "[%Y]", "%Y-%m-%d", "%Y--%m-%d", "%Y--%m--%d", "%d/%m/%Y",
    "%Y/%m/%d", "%Y%m%d", "%Y----", "%Y.%m.%d", "%d.%m.%Y"],
  "components": {
    "months": {
      "English": {
        "January": "01", "February": "02", "March": "03", "April": "04",
        "May": "05", "June": "06", "July": "07", "August": "08",
        "September": "09", "October": "10", "November": "11", "December": "12"
      },
      "French": {
        "Janvier": "01", "Février": "02", "Mars": "03", "Avril": "04",
        "Mai": "05", "Juin": "06", "Juillet": "07", "Août": "08",
        "Septembre": "09", "Octobre": "10", "Novembre": "11", "Décembre": "12"
      },
      "Dutch": {
        "Januari": "01", "Februari": "02", "Maart": "03", "April": "04",
        "Mei": "05", "Juni": "06", "Juli": "07", "Augustus": "08",
        "September": "09", "Oktober": "10", "November": "11", "December": "12"
      },
      "German": {
        "Januar": "01", "Februar": "02", "März": "03", "April": "04",
        "Mai": "05", "Juni": "06", "Juli": "07", "August": "08",
        "September": "09", "Oktober": "10", "November": "11", "Dezember": "12"
      }
    },
    "keywords": {
      "before": "(?:before|avant|Avant)",
      "after": "(?:after|après|Après|apres|Apres)",
      "between": "(?:entre|Entre|between|Between)",
      "and": "(?:and|et|Et)",
      "or": "(?:or|ou|of)",
      "circa": "(?:c[.]|ca[.]|Vers)",
      "flourish": "(?:f|fl|flo|flor|flor[.] ca|Floruit)[.]{0,1}"
    }
  }
}
```

```

"year": "(\\d{3,4})",
"century": "([1-9]|1[0-9]|20|21)",
"month": "(0[1-9]|1[012])",
"day": "([0]?[1-9]|[1-2][0-9]|3[01])",
"roman_numeral": "(X{0,3}|IX|V?I{0,3})"
},
"rules": {
  "range_with_and_written_month": {
    "pattern":
"%{keywords.before}s\\s+%(months.generic)s\\s+%(year)s\\s+%(keywords.and)s\\s+%(keywords.after)s\\s
+%(months.generic)s\\s+%(year)s",
    "template": "%s-%s/%s-%s"
  },
  "range_with_and_year": {
    "pattern":
"%{keywords.before}s\\s+%(year)s\\s+%(keywords.and)s\\s+%(keywords.after)s\\s+%(year)s",
    "template": "[%s/%s]"
  },
  "between_years": {
    "pattern": "%{keywords.between}s\\s+%(year)s\\s+%(keywords.and)s\\s+%(year)s",
    "template": "[%s..%s]"
  },
  "before_written_month_year": {
    "pattern": "%{keywords.before}s\\s+%(months.generic)s\\s+%(year)s",
    "template": "[%s-%s]"
  },
  "before_dash_date": {
    "pattern": "%{keywords.before}s\\s+%(day)s/%(month)s/%(year)s",
    "template": "[%s-%s-%s]"
  },
  "after_written_month_year": {
    "pattern": "%{keywords.after}s\\s+%(months.generic)s\\s+%(year)s",
    "template": "[%s-%s.]"
  },
  "written_month_year": {
    "pattern": "(%{months.generic)s\\s+%(year)s"
  },
  "before_year": {
    "pattern": "%{keywords.before}s\\s+%(year)s",
    "template": "[%s]"
  },
  "after_year": {
    "pattern": "%{keywords.after}s\\s+%(year)s$",
    "template": "[%s.]"
  },
  "year_month": {
    "pattern": "%(year)s-%(month)s(?:-XX)?(?:!-\\d)",
    "template": "%s-%s"
  },
  "year_or": {
    "pattern": "%(year)s\\s+%(keywords.or)s\\s+%(year)s",
    "template": "[%s,%s]"
  },
  "year_or_brackets": {

```

```

        "pattern": "%(year)s\\s+\\((keywords.or)s\\s+%(year)s\\)",
        "template": "[%s,%s]"
    },
    "uncertain_year": {
        "pattern": "^%(year)s\\s+\\{?",
        "template": "%s?"
    },
    "flourish_year": {
        "pattern": "%(keywords.flourish)s\\s*%(year)s",
        "template": "[%s]"
    },
    "flourish_century": {
        "pattern": "%(keywords.flourish)s\\s*(\\d{2})(?:[-]|\\.)",
        "template": "[%sXX]"
    },
    "circa_year": {
        "pattern": "%(keywords.circa)s\\s*%(year)s",
        "template": "%s~"
    },
    "one_of_two_years_dash": {
        "pattern": "%(year)s\\s*-\\s*%(year)s",
        "template": "[%s,%s]"
    },
    "one_of_two_years_slash": {
        "pattern": "%(year)s\\s*\\/\\s*%(year)s",
        "template": "[%s,%s]"
    },
    "years_slash_abbreviation": {
        "pattern": "%(year)s\\s*\\(\\d{1,2})"
    },
    "date_and_text": {
        "pattern": "%(year)s{-}?%(month)s{-}?%(day)s(?:,|\\s)*(?:\\b\\w+\\b\\s*)*",
        "template": "%s-%s-%s"
    },
    "year_and_text": {
        "pattern": "%(year)s(?:,|\\s)*(?:\\b\\w+\\b\\s*)*",
        "template": "%s"
    },
    "century": {
        "pattern": "^%(century)s(?:X|-)?(?:\\d)",
        "template": "%sXX"
    }
}
}

```